

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MECHANISMS OF ACTION OF NIO NANOPARTICLES IN THE HUMAN BODY IN COMBINATION WITH GREEN SYNTHESIS

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Abstract

Nanoparticles are small particles ranging in size from 1 to 100 nanometers (nm). Due to their size, nanoparticles have unique physical and chemical properties that differ from their counterparts. The synthesis and properties of nickel oxide nanoparticles (NiO NPs) constitute an important area of research due to their superior ferromagnetic properties and chemical stability. It is used as an inexpensive catalyst due to its natural abundance and ability to control reactions in alternative ways. They have countless biomedical applications, including magnetic resonance imaging, cell separation, drug delivery, biomedical detection, and more. In addition to these, in recent times, with the development of nanotechnology, the Green nanotechnology method has been used in the synthesis of nanoparticles. In this method, nanoparticles are synthesized using various biological systems, including yeast, algae, and bacteria.

Keywords: Nanoparticles (NP), metal and metal oxide nanoparticles, Ni and NiO nanoparticles

Nanoparticles are small particles ranging in size from 1 to 100 nanometers (nm). Due to their size, nanoparticles have unique physical and chemical properties that differ from their counterparts. Of these, the unique feature of energy storage is widely used in the development of electronics and biomedical fields (1). One of the most important advantages of nanoparticles (NPs) is their high surface-to-volume ratio, which increases their reactivity and catalytic activity. Physical and chemical, color or optical properties of NPs depend on their size and shape. The melting and phase transition temperatures of NPs are low, and the band gap increases as the size of NPs decreases. In addition, the small size of nanoparticles allows them to cross biological barriers such as cell membranes, making them highly effective in drug delivery and medical imaging applications. Also, their optical and electronic properties make them useful in electronics and energy storage applications (2).

Despite their beneficial properties for their application, nanoparticles can also pose potential risks to human health and the environment. For example, their small size may facilitate their entry into the human body through inhalation or ingestion, leading to their ability to interact with biological systems in ways that are not yet fully understood (Auffan et al., 2009).

Nanoparticles can be synthesized from a variety of materials, including metals, metal oxides, polymers, and carbon-based materials, using a variety of methods such as chemical synthesis, physical precipitation, and biological methods. The choice of material in the synthesis method can significantly affect the properties of the resulting nanoparticles (3).

Top-down and bottom-up synthesis protocols are accepted for nanoparticle synthesis methods. In addition, Green nanotechnology method has been used in the synthesis of nanoparticles with the development of nanotechnology in recent times. In this method, nanoparticles are synthesized using various biological systems including yeast, algae, and bacteria (Salem, 2023).

The synthesis mechanism of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles with plant extract occurs in three stages: activation stage, growth stage and termination stage. In the activation phase, metal ions are reduced and reduced metal atoms become nuclei. During the growth phase, small NPs aggregate together to form larger nanoparticles. In this process, called Ostwald ripening, the thermodynamic stability of nanoparticles increases. In the finishing stage, the nanoparticles take their final form. The final product is air dried or air calcined to produce the metal oxide. NiO NP is also used for research in this field.

Nickel nanoparticles are a new product with many properties such as high surface energy, high magnetism, low melting point, high surface area, high reactivity, biocompatibility, resistance to bacteria, anti-inflammatory properties and environmental compatibility, low flash point. Nickel nanoparticles are widely used in modern industries such as catalysts, sensors, electrocatalysts, photocatalysts, biosensors, heat exchangers, and electronic applications (Zhang et al., 2003; Sivulka, 2005). Their widespread use in humans and the environment increases the potential risk associated with their toxicity. Meanwhile, NPs are used in numerous biomedical fields, including cell isolation, drug

delivery, magnetic resonance imaging, biomedical diagnostics, etc. Anhydrous and aqueous nickel nanoparticles prepared by sonication, radiolytic and chemical reduction, and freeze-drying reactions can react chemically in environments.

It is important to produce nickel nanoparticles at an affordable cost that is environmentally sustainable, economically viable, and socially compatible. In the production of nanometals, green synthesis is considered faster and cheaper.

Metal nanoparticles produced by green synthesis have different sizes and morphologies. Organic functional groups in plants play an active role as reducing, protecting and stabilizing agents in the production of nanoparticles (4). Nanomaterials prepared by this method have high polydispersity, well-defined dimensions and thermodynamic stability. Green-based synthesis methods such as leaf extract, stem bark, root, and plant exudates are thought to be more suitable for the synthesis of metallic nanomaterials (5).

Nanobiotechnology - This rapidly growing field is widely applied at various commercial levels, namely agriculture, cosmetics, catalysis, food, bioremediation, optics, cancer treatment, drug delivery, genetic engineering, and many others (6). Metal oxide nanoparticles (MONPs) produced by green synthesis have attracted much attention due to their safe, energy-efficient, environmentally friendly, and reproducible properties (7). Nanosized particles are considered effective for research due to their variability, physical, optical, mechanical, magnetic, sensing and electrical properties compared to their bulk counterparts (8). Nickel oxide nanoparticles (NiONPs) are widely used in research due to their remarkable intrinsic properties such as chemical stability, p-type semiconductor, nanodevice fabrication, electron transfer potential, sensing, electro-catalysis, optoelectronic capabilities, and drug delivery. So far, NiONPs have been studied for their anti-inflammatory, cytotoxic, and pollutant adsorption properties (9).

Recently, NiONPs have been prepared by phytochemical means and explored for various biological applications. It should be noted that many plants, viz. *Agathosma betulina* (10), *Geranium wallichianum* (11), *Bergenia ciliata* (12), *Rhamnus virgata* (6), *Nephelium lappaceum* (13), *Berberis balochistanica* (14) and *Tamarix* (15) were used for the synthesis of NiONPs.

E. angustifolia (EIA) is reported to alleviate several serious diseases such as jaundice, cancer, asthma, inflammation, osteoarthritis, diarrhea, gastrointestinal problems and rheumatoid arthritis. According to ethnobotanical data, various EIA extracts have shown antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and wound healing properties (16). In this study, EIA-based NiONPs were characterized and screened for anticancer, antileishmanial, antimicrobial, antioxidant, enzyme inhibition potential and biocompatibility analysis.

Green synthesis with NiO *E. Angustifolia* gives very important results as an enzyme inhibitor in diseases such as cancer and diabetes, which are very important to treat today. Also, *L. tropica* causes an infectious disease, leishmaniasis. Leishmaniasis is an NTD

(neglected tropical infection) that is mainly spread by sand fly bites. In this study, different concentrations of EIA-NiONPs (range: 3.91-500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were tested against amastigotes and promastigotes of *L. tropica* and showed significant positive results.

Also, synthesis of nickel oxide nanoparticles using plant extract and their antibacterial effects on *Streptococcus mutans* were evaluated. Tooth decay is known as the most common infectious disease of people in the world. The increasing index of dental caries in the world shows the failure of prevention of oral diseases. *Streptococcus mutans* bacteria produce acid over time, causing tooth damage and decay. Nanomaterials with appropriate functionality, high conductivity, extremely large surface area, significant reactivity, unique mechanical properties, and non-bacterial resistance can be considered promising tools for antimicrobial and antiviral applications. In this study, nickel oxide (NiO) nanoparticles with a size between 2 and 16 nm were synthesized by a simple method with the environmentally friendly *Stevia* natural sweetener. In addition, their different concentrations were studied on *S. mutans* bacteria by applying the broth dilution method. The results showed that these spherical NiO nanoparticles have effective bacteriostatic activity on gram-positive cocci (17).

The synthesis and properties of nickel oxide nanoparticles (NiO NPs) constitute an important area of research due to their superior ferromagnetic properties and chemical stability. It is used as an inexpensive catalyst due to its natural abundance and ability to control reactions in alternative ways. They have countless biomedical applications, including magnetic resonance imaging, cell separation, drug delivery, biomedical detection, and more. (Jaji et al., 2020) *Klebsiella pneumoniae*; Significant antibacterial properties against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *S. Aureus* and more bacteria have been studied (Yulizar et al., 2021, Iqbal et al., 2019). Uddin et al. (2021) reported antifungal activity of NiO NPs against *Aspergillus Niger*, *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium oxysporum*. Many studies have successfully tested the anticancer and antiparasitic properties of NiO NPs. These include cytotoxicity study against A549 cell culture, effect of NiO NPs on HeLa cancer cells, MCF-7 cancer line models and HepG2 cells (Lingaraju et al., 2020, Ariyanta et al., 2021, Angel Ezhilarasi et al., 2018, Ramalingam et al., 2019). Iqbal and others. showed that NiO NPs can be antiparasitic against strains of Amastigotes, promastigotes and *Leishmania tropica* He also reported that NiO NPs have compatibility with macrophages and RBCs (IC50 value more than 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). As a result of research, NiO NPs have also been found to have antioxidant properties (Iqbal et al., 2019) (18).

NiO NPs have advantages as well as disadvantages in many application areas. Thus, various factors affect environmental pollution in the world. These factors include inorganic ions, organic pollutants, radioactive isotopes, gaseous pollutants and nanoparticles. Heavy metals enter the human body in four ways: through contaminated food; occurs due to inhalation of

air from the atmosphere, ingestion of contaminated water, skin contact in pharmaceutical, agricultural, residential and industrial areas.

Hepatotoxicity of Ni lin poses a great threat to health by changing biochemical functions in the body. (Das et al., 2008).

Ni nanoparticles are widely used in industry. For this reason, in the body

the resulting problems cause concern to the world population.

Nickel as a low molecular density lipophilic compound in the gastrointestinal tract

It is absorbed through various ligands and ions of nickel located in the intestine

helps absorption. Nickel has a wide range of carcinogenic mechanisms.

Another disadvantage is that activation of ATF-1 by Nickel leads to increased angiogenesis and stimulate the growth of tumor cells (19).

One of the most common disadvantages of nickel nanoparticles is skin

allergies, it is also an immunotoxic agent in the human body. Such reactions are from soil to nickel-containing metal objects from water and metal

can occur from direct contact with jewelry. Nickel-based Factory workers are constantly exposed to nickel fumes and dust Research shows that constant breathing of nickel dust and nickel fumes causes various respiratory diseases (bronchitis, asthma). In addition, lung and nose cancer are more common in people working in such factories (20). Research has shown that the causes of nickel-related cancer are genetic, epigenetic factors and oxidative stress. Some nickel compounds cause cell proliferation, which can lead to mild DNA mutations. Drinking water from nickel-contaminated basins can cause many effects - dizziness, headache, general weakness (21).

Thus, NiONPs are applied to inhibit various in vitro, microbial, cancer and leishmanial cells. Synthesized NiO NPs have been examined spectroscopically and microscopically with plant and fruit extracts in many research areas and found to be helpful in preventing harmful substances. Nanosized particles made using natural NPs are considered to be bio-safe in nature. However, side effects are also inevitable. The environment is heavily polluted with metals, which affects human health. All the researched materials make us aware of the negative effects caused by these metals, the symptoms that have arisen. Thus, new researches should be continued to overcome the adverse effects of metal pollution, metal NPs.

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